

Supplementary Materials

This document provides additional figures and details supporting the main article: *"The Software Observatory: aggregating and analysing software metadata for trend computation and FAIR assessment"*, Eva Martín del Pico , 2025.

Figure S1: System architecture of the Software Observatory within the OpenEBench platform. The Observatory is implemented as a single-page application embedded in the OpenEBench (OEB) web platform. The user interface—referred to in this paper as the “Observatory interface”—is rendered by the OEB UI server, built with NuxtJS. This interface communicates via HTTP with two backend services: (1) the Observatory API (Python/FastAPI), which handles data ingestion, scoring, and metadata integration; and (2) the FAIRsoft Evaluator GitHub App API (NodeJS/Express), which manages authenticated interactions with GitHub. GitHub authentication and permissions are handled using two GitHub Apps (i.e., registered integration entities, not visual components): the metadata extraction app retrieves metadata from public repositories, while the contribution app creates pull requests to add or update structured metadata such as `CITATION.cff` files. All services are containerized using Docker, and the GitHub App API is configured through environment variables that include App IDs and private keys. This modular architecture enables secure, scalable, and semi-automated FAIR metadata workflows within the Software Observatory.

Data Source	Raw records	Collection Method	Access Method	Metadata Format
bio.tools	36,665	OpenEBench ¹	REST API	Structured (JSON)
GitHub	3,918	GitHub APIs	REST/GraphQL	Structured (JSON)
Bioconda	10,215	Bioconda recipes repo	Git	Structured (YAML)
Bioconductor	3,499	Bioconductor packages	Git	Structured (DESCRIPTION + CITATION)
Galaxy	1,543	OpenEBench ¹	REST API	Structured (JSON)
ToolShed	7,095	ToolShed repositories	Mercurial (hg)	Structured (XML)
SourceForge	3,007	Web scraping	Web scraping	Semi-structured (HTML)

Table S1: Overview of metadata sources used in the Software Observatory.

¹ OpenEBench technical monitoring retrieves metadata from the [ELIXIR Software Ecosystem](#).

Component	Repository URL
Metadata Importers	
bio.tools importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/opeb-tools-importer
GitHub importer	https://github.com/inab/github-importer
Bioconda importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/bioconda-recipes
Bioconductor importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/bioconductor-importer-v2
Galaxy importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/opeb-tools-importer
ToolShed importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/toolshed-importer
SourceForge importer	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/elixir/software-observatory/sourceforge-importer
Processing and Integration Pipeline	
Transformation, normal- ization, enrichment, inte- gration and calculations	https://github.com/inab/research-software-etl
License normalisation	https://github.com/inab/licenses-mapping
User-Facing and Backend Services	
OpenEBench UI	https://github.com/inab/openEBench-nuxt
Observatory API	https://github.com/inab/observatory-api
FAIRsoft GitHub API	https://github.com/inab/github-metadata-api

Table S2: List of Software Observatory components grouped by function, with links to their respective repositories.

Figure S2: FAIRness Trends Analysis interface of the Software Observatory, shown here for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community. A key feature is the collection selector at the top, which allows filtering by project or community (e.g., VEIS, ELIXIR-ES, Impact-Data). This selector is consistently available across the Trends, Data, and FAIRsoft Scoreboard sections, facilitating focused analysis of software FAIRness within specific domains.

Figure S3: "Licensing" panel of the FAIRness Trends Analysis interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S4: "Versioning" and "Repositories and Version control" panels of the FAIRness Trends Analysis interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S5: "Publication" panel of the FAIRness Trends Analysis interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S6: "Findability" panel of the FAIRsoft Indicator Scoreboard interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S7: "Accessibility" panel of the FAIRsoft Indicator Scoreboard interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

- **I1 – Data format standards and practices:**
Does the software use and support standard data formats and good data handling practices?
 - Input/output formats follow accepted standards (e.g., EDAM ontology).
 - Input/output formats can be validated using schemas (e.g., JSON, XML, RDF).
 - Multiple input/output formats are supported or convertible.
- **I2 – Software integration**
Can the software be used easily with other tools or in workflows?
 - The software is available as a library or has an API version.
 - The software can be deployed on platforms like Galaxy or VREs.
- **I3 – Dependencies availability**
Are the software's dependencies documented and accessible?
 - The software explicitly lists its dependencies.
 - Dependencies are bundled or accessible through external resources.
 - The software is available through systems like Bioconda or Galaxy Europe.

Figure S8: "Interoperability" panel of the FAIRsoft Indicator Scoreboard interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S9: "Reusability" panel of the FAIRsoft Indicator Scoreboard interface of the Software Observatory, shown for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community.

Figure S10: Integrated metadata overview for the ELIXIR Proteomics Community in the Software Observatory. This composite view illustrates the software integration and metadata coverage achieved by the Software Observatory. The top section displays the number of software tools contributed by each metadata source after harmonization. The bottom section presents metadata coverage across sources for key features such as version, license, and documentation. Dots indicate availability of metadata fields, while bars reflect the number of entries in the final dataset containing each feature. Together, these panels highlight both the scale and variability of metadata integration, which the FAIRsoft Evaluator addresses to support FAIRness assessments.

Figure S11: "Coverage" panel of the Data interface of the Software Observatory.

Figure S12: Initial page of the FAIRsoft Evaluator within the Software Observatory. This interface guides users through the evaluation process by first selecting the source of the software's metadata. Users can choose to retrieve metadata from the Software Observatory's database, a GitHub repository, or an external metadata file in maSMP format [1]. The page also outlines the four main steps of the tool: Retrieve, Refine, Evaluate, and Act.

Figure S13: Second step of the FAIRsoft Evaluator within the Software Observatory: selecting a software entry to evaluate. After choosing the metadata source, users are prompted to select a specific software tool from the Observatory's database. The interface supports search and auto-completion, and each entry is labeled by type (e.g., LIB for library, CMD for command-line tool), facilitating targeted evaluation of diverse software categories.

Figure S14: Metadata refinement step in the FAIRsoft Evaluator within the Software Observatory. After selecting the software to evaluate, users are guided through an interactive interface to review and edit metadata fields grouped under categories (e.g., Identity, License, Documentation, Interoperability). The first panel summarizes the completion status across all categories, using visual indicators to show which criteria are fulfilled. The second panel shows the detailed editing view for the “Identity” and “Accessibility / License” sections, allowing users to update key metadata elements such as name, description, software type, license, and associated URLs. This refinement step is identical across all input modes—whether the metadata is sourced from the Software Observatory, a GitHub repository, or an external metadata file.

Figure S15: Summary of results in the FAIRsoft Evaluator. Radar plots visualize performance across the sub-indicators for each FAIR principle. Findability and Accessibility are visible in the image.

Figure S16: Detail of Findability results in the FAIRsoft Evaluator, focusing on indicator F2: Existence of metadata. This view allows users to understand not only whether their software passes or fails a given indicator, but also why. Each indicator includes a clear definition, an explanation of its relevance, and a description of how it is assessed. In this example, the software passes because it uses standardised vocabularies (EDAM terms) to describe both topics and operations. By making the evaluation logic explicit, this interface helps users judge the relevance of each indicator for their specific context and offers concrete guidance on how to improve their FAIRness score.

References

- [1] Giraldo Olga, Geist Lukas, Quiñones Nelson, Solanki Dhwani, Rebholz-Schuhmann Dietrich, and Castro Leyla Jael. Machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (maSMP Ontology). April 2023.